

Effect of compost and single super phosphate on the uptake of cadmium by Radish (*Raphanus sativus* L.)

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Abstract : A field experiment was conducted to find out the effect of organic matter and single super phosphate on the uptake of cadmium by Radish (*Raphanus sativus* L.) on the alluvial soil of Sheila Dhar Institute experimental farm, Allahabad. Three levels of organic matter (0, 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹), single super phosphate (0, 100 and 200 kg ha⁻¹), Cd (0, 5 and 10 mg kg⁻¹) were applied as compost, SSP and CdCl₂, respectively. Addition of 200 kg ha⁻¹ SSP increased the maximum dry biomass yield of Radish by 31.7% over the control. The application of 10 mg kg⁻¹ Cd maximum reduce dry biomass yield of Radish by 17.5% over the control and registered the highest accumulation of Cd in shoot and root of Radish by 2.0, 2.4 fold over the control, respectively. Therefore, 200 kg ha⁻¹ SSP applications may be recommended to enhance biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. and phytoremediation of cadmium-contaminated soil through soil-plant rhizospheric processes.

Keywords : Cadmium, compost, SSP, radish, uptake.

Introduction

The contamination of soils with toxic metals has become a major environmental concern in many parts of the world due to rapid industrialization, increased urbanization, modern agricultural practices and inappropriate waste disposal methods.

The plant used in the phytoremediation technique must have a considerable capacity of metal absorption, its accumulation and strength to decrease the treatment time. Many families of vascular plants have been identified as metal hyperaccumulators^{1,2} and many of them belongs to Brassicaceae. These hyperaccumulators are metal selective, having slow growth rate, produce small amounts of biomass and can be used in their natural habitats only³. There are many other processes which govern metal accumulation in plants e.g. metal mobilization and uptake from soils, compartmentation and sequestration within the root, efficient of xylem to transport metal, distribution of metal in the aerial parts, sequestration and storage in leafy cells⁴.

Heavy metal uptake by plants strongly depends on several soil and plant factors^{5,6}. It is known that only a

small amount of the total Pb in soils may be taken up by plants and the translocation of Pb from roots to tops is greatly limited. Cadmium can be more readily taken up by plants, and relatively high concentrations may occur in crops⁵. Many works have been conducted to elucidate the mechanism of heavy metal absorption by plants in solution culture⁷⁻⁹.

Results and discussion

Effect of Cd × compost interaction on dry biomass yield of Raphanus sativus L. :

The data presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1 indicates that addition of organic matter (compost) individually was observed significant in crop. Addition of compost @ 20 t ha⁻¹ increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 22.7% increase over the control¹⁰. Added single doses of Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ and Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ (T₄) individually reduced the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 4.5% and 17.3% over the control, respectively. The addition of combined treatment Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + compost 10 t ha⁻¹ increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 10.9% over the control. The

Table 1. Effect of Cd × compost interaction on dry biomass yield (g/plots) and Cd concentration (mg kg⁻¹) of *Raphanus sativus* L.

Cd-rate (mg kg ⁻¹)	Compost t ha ⁻¹	Yield g/plot	Cd concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)	
			Shoot	Root
0	0	375	0.65	1.00
	10	420	0.55	0.80
	20	460	0.43	0.75
5	0	358	1.00	1.93
	10	416	0.95	1.20
	20	456	0.78	1.13
10	0	310	1.33	2.45
	10	353	1.24	1.85
	20	435	1.00	1.75
SE =		4.98	0.06	0.05
CD =		10.56	0.12	0.11

Fig. 1. Effect of Cd × compost interaction on dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. (g/plots).

addition of combined treatment Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + compost 20 t ha⁻¹ and Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ + compost 20 t ha⁻¹ marginally increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 21.6% and 16% over the control, respectively¹¹.

The study of Cd × compost interaction concluded that Cd alone decreased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. but with compost yield was affected variably. Compost alone increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. but the percentage increase was less compared to control.

Effect of Cd × compost interaction on Cd concentration in shoot and root of Raphanus sativus L. :

The data (Table 1) indicated that the effect of Cd, compost and Cd × compost interaction was observed significant. Accumulation of Cd in roots and shoot of

plants significantly increased and indicated greater relative Cd accumulation from control to Cd added plots. Application of Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ + 20 t ha⁻¹ compost (T₉) increases the accumulation 1.5 fold (mean 1.0 mg kg⁻¹) and 1.7 fold (mean 1.7 mg kg⁻¹) of Cd in shoots and root of *Raphanus sativus* L. over the control, respectively. Application of Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ (T₇) increased the highest accumulation of Cd in shoot and root of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 1.33–2.45 mg kg⁻¹ (2.0–2.45 folds) over the control, respectively^{12–14} (Figs. 2 and 3).

Effect of Cd × SSP interaction on dry biomass yield of Raphanus sativus L. :

The data presented in Table 2 and Fig. 4 revealed that Cd and SSP were observed significant on influencing the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. The application

Fig. 2. Effect of Cd × compost interaction on Cd concentration in shoot of *Raphanus sativus* L. (mg kg⁻¹).

Fig. 3. Effect of Cd × compost interaction on Cd concentration in root of *Raphanus sativus* L. (mg kg⁻¹).

of SSP @ 200 kg ha⁻¹ (T₃) increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 31.7% increase over the control. Added single doses of Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ and Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ individually reduced the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 2.7% and 17.5% over the control, respectively. The addition of combined treatment Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + SSP 100 kg ha⁻¹ increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 21.5% over the control. The application of combined treatment Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + SSP 200 kg ha⁻¹ individually increased the dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 23.9% over the control¹⁵.

Effect of Cd × SSP interaction on Cd concentration in shoot and root of Raphanus sativus L. :

The data (Table 2) indicates that the effects of Cd, SSP and Cd × SSP interactions were observed significant. Accumulation of Cd in roots and shoot of plants significantly increased and indicated greater relative Cd accumulation from control to Cd added plots. Application of Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ + SSP 200 kg ha⁻¹ (T₉) increased the accumulation of Pb 1.0 fold (mean 0.70 mg kg⁻¹) and 1.1 fold (mean 1.3 mg kg⁻¹) in shoots and root of *Raphanus sativus* L. over the control, respectively (Figs. 5 and 6).

Table 2. Effect of Cd × SSP interaction on dry biomass yield (g/plots) and Cd concentration (mg kg⁻¹) of *Raphanus sativus* L.

Cd-rate (mg kg ⁻¹)	SSP kg ha ⁻¹	Yield g/plot	Cd concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)	
			Shoot	Root
0	0	331	0.64	1.20
	100	419	0.55	0.80
	200	436	0.42	0.75
5	0	322	0.97	1.63
	100	402	0.80	1.30
	200	410	0.72	1.26
10	0	273	1.10	2.40
	100	318	1.00	1.40
	200	340	0.70	1.30
SE =		6.28	0.04	0.09
CD =		13.3	0.09	0.19

Fig. 4. Effect of Cd × SSP interaction on dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. (g/plots).

Application of Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ increased the accumulation of Cd in shoot and root of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 1.10–2.40 mg kg⁻¹ over the control, respectively¹⁶.

Heavy metals are mobile and can be taken up easily by the plants. They occur in the soil in soluble form as salts¹⁷. However, only soluble, exchangeable and chelated metallic species in the soil are mobile and in available form¹⁸. Mobility is an important factor in regulating the availability and solubility of heavy metals in the soil and soil solution. The mobility depends on their speciation in the soil, which in turn depends on parameters such as organic matter and mineral composition, pH of the soil¹⁹. Mobility of heavy metals is also related to their immobilization in the solid soil. Metal accumulation in plant depends on plant species, growth stages and types of soil and metal, soil conditions, weather and environment²⁰.

Materials and method :

Experimental site :

The experimental site is situated in northern India at 25°57'N latitude and 81°50'E longitude on south-east facing slopes of comparable inclination at altitudes between 200 and 80 m above sea level. A sandy clay loam soil, derived from sewage-sludge irrigated Indo-Gangetic alluvial soils of SDI farm situated on the confluence of Ganga and Yamuna alluvial deposit, was sampled from Allahabad city, India. The properties of the soil were : pH 8.0, EC 0.28 dSm⁻¹, organic matter (K₂Cr₂O₇ oxidation) 5.6 g kg⁻¹, total N 0.08%, total P 0.04%, CEC 19.8 C mol (P) kg⁻¹ and DTPA–Cd 0.38 mg kg⁻¹. The texture comprised of sand (>0.2 mm) 56.0%, silt (0.002–0.2 mm) 20.0% and clay (<0.002 mm) 24.0%.

Fig. 5. Effect of Cd × SSP interaction on Cd concentration in shoot of *Raphanus sativus* L. (mg kg⁻¹).

Fig. 6. Effect of Cd × SSP interaction on Cd concentration in root of *Raphanus sativus* L. (mg kg⁻¹).

Soil analysis :

Preparation of DTPA solution :

Diethyl triamine penta acetic acid (DTPA) solution was prepared by a method developed by Lindsay and Norvell²¹ used to extract the available heavy metals in soil samples.

Extraction of soil with DTPA solution :

Five gram soil and 20 ml DTPA solution was added

and the contents were shaken for two hours and then filtrate through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The clean filtrate was used for the estimation of Cd by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer.

Soil pH was measured with 1 : 2.5 soil water ratio using ELICO pH meter. Organic carbon was determined by rapid titration method²². Total nitrogen was determined by using Kjeldahl digestion method²¹. Available

nitrogen was determined by Alkaline Permanganate method²³. Potash was estimated by Flame Photometer method. Phosphate was determined by Olsen's method with the help of colorimeter. Cation exchange capacity was determined by using neutral normal ammonium acetate solution²⁴.

Experimental

After systematic survey factorial experiment was conducted to study the effect of compost and single super phosphate on the uptake of cadmium by Radish (*Raphanus sativus* L). The experiment was replicated thrice with nine treatments and conducted in completely factorial randomized block design (factorial RBD). After 24 h of the treatment seeds were sown. Soil moisture was maintained by irrigating the crops at interval of 5–6 days. Vegetables were harvested at 45 days after sowing (DAS). Radish was grown successively in the 27 pots (each of 1 m² in area). The treatments of Cd × compost and Cd × SSP relationship consisted of 0, 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹ compost and 0, 100 and 200 kg ha⁻¹ single super phosphate along with 0, 5 and 10 mg kg⁻¹ Cd. The source of Cd, organic matter and phosphate were CdCl₂, compost and SSP respectively.

Plant analysis :

Heavy metals in plants were determined by tri-acid mixture (HNO₃, conc. H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ in 5 : 1 : 1 ratio)²⁵. Heavy metal in soil and plant were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectrometry (ICP-AES; Model - LABTEM, Perkin-Elmer, Inc.) at Central Environment Pollution Control Lab, Indian Farmer Fertilizer Cooperative (IFFCO) Ltd., Phulpur Unit, Ghiya Nagar, Phulpur, Allahabad.

Statistical analysis :

Data were analyzed by factorial analysis of variation (ANOVA) using various treatments as independent factors with the help of the sum of square (SS) and degree of freedom (DF). The standard error (SE) is given by $SE = \sqrt{2V_E/n}$, where, V_E is the variance due to the error, n is the number of replications, and the critical difference (CD) is given by $CD = SE_{diff.} \times t_{5\%}$ ($t_{5\%} = 2.042$ at $DF_{error} = 30$ was observed) and standard deviation (Syx) were determined in accordance with Motulsky and Christopoulos (2003)²⁶.

Conclusion

Single super phosphate treated plots registered the highest dry biomass yield of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 31.7%. Application of SSP @ 200 kg ha⁻¹ was found most effective in boosting the dry biomass content of crop. Cd @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ influenced the dry biomass content diminutively, which was recorded 17.5% decrease over the control plots in *Raphanus sativus* L.

Compost treated plots registered the highest dry biomass yield by 22.7% for *Raphanus sativus* L. in the effect of Cd × compost interaction. Application of Cd 10 mg kg⁻¹ increased the highest accumulation of Cd in shoot and root of *Raphanus sativus* L. by 1.33–2.45 mg kg⁻¹ respectively.

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